

is about 50 cm lower than normal.

The interaction between planting method and fertilizer application significantly influenced grain yield (Table 2). Adding NP or NPK increased yield of broadcast seeded rice over the control and N alone.

For transplanted rice, adding NP or NPK significantly increased yields above

the control and N alone. Applying N alone decreased yield 64% below that of the control as there was a significant reduction in panicle number and filled grains/panicle.

Adding N alone appeared to aggravate Al toxicity, which reduced root growth. Adding P appeared to enhance root development and therefore nutrient absorption.

Adding K did not affect yield.

The adverse effect of N alone on grain yield was less pronounced in the broadcast crop because it had higher plant density than the transplanted crop. Results suggest that closer spacing and P application are essential to improve density of the transplanted crop and therefore grain yield. □

Factors affecting critical P level for rice

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We conducted greenhouse and laboratory studies on soils with different texture, Olsen's extractable P, and CaCO₃ content. Olsen's P was higher in submerged soils than in air-dried soil (Table 1). Rice grain yield was significantly correlated with

Table 2. Effect of submergence and soil type on critical Olsen's level. Ludhiana, India.

Soil texture and type	Air-dried soil	Critical Olsen's P ^a		
		Submergence period (d)		
		1	3	7
Coarse (sand-sandy loam)	7.4 (0.89**)	12.5 (0.85**)	19.2 (0.75**)	19.9 (0.61**)
Medium (loam)	8.0 (0.99**)	11.1 (0.91**)	10.6 (0.88**)	10.5 (0.69**)
Fine (silty loam-silty clay loam)	8.4 (0.99**)	10.6 (0.82**)	13.4 (0.86**)	15.1 (0.91**)
High CaCO ₃ (loamy-sand-clay)	7.8 (0.71**)	19.0 (0.60**)	20.9 (0.54**)	22.7 (0.52**)

^a Figures in parentheses indicate the R² value. ** = significant at 1% level.

Table 1. Effect of submergence on Olsen's extractable P, Ludhiana, India.

Soil texture type	Air dried	Extractable P (ppm) ^a after submergence for			
		1 d	3 d	7 d	15 d
Coarse (sand-sandy loam)	0.5-8.5	1.5-19.5	2.5-22.5	5-20.5	5-20
Medium (loam)	1-10.5	2.5-13.5	3.5-14	4.2-13.5	4.5-16.5
Fine (silty loam-silty clay loam)	4-10.5	5-13.5	7.5-16	11-19	13-22
High CaCO ₃ (loamy sand-clay)	4.2-8.5 (5.6)	8.5-21.5 (13.8)	10-24 (15.2)	11.5-25.5 (16.6)	12.5-27.5 (18.8)

^a Figures in parentheses indicate the mean value.

Olsen's extractable P. Critical Olsen's P level for rice was calculated by quadratic regression equations. Critical P depended upon soil texture, CaCO₃ content, and period of submergence (Table 2). □

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Causes for different response to and availability of P in rice and wheat ecosystems

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We studied rice and wheat response to applied P in the greenhouse on soil with different texture, Olsen's P, and CaCO₃. We also noted the effect of temperature and moisture on Olsen's P.

Bray's percent yield was higher for rice than for wheat (Table 1). CaCO₃ soil content did not affect Bray's percent

Table 1. Effect of soil type on Bray's yield of rice and wheat, Ludhiana, India.

Soil	Soils (no.)	pH ^a	Olsen's P ^a (ppm)	Bray's yield ^b (%)	
				Rice	Wheat
Coarse	5	7.5-8.9 (8.2)	0.5-8.5 (4.1)	85.3	60.0
Medium	5	8-9.1 (8.4)	1-10.5 (4.5)	85.0	64.6
Fine	4	7-8.3 (7.9)	4-10.5 (6.6)	94.6	75.7
High CaCO ₃ (>8%)					
Fine	2	8-8.1 (8.1)	4.3-8.5 (6.4)	95.2	58.7
Coarse	2	8-8.2 (8.1)	4.5-5.5 (5)	84.4	64.7

^a Numbers in parentheses are the mean.

^b Bray's percent yield = $\frac{\text{yield without P}}{\text{yield with 30 ppm P}} \times 100$.